

SOCIAL MEDIA

Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube,
TikTok, WhatsApp, WeChat, Didiun,
Didi, Weibo, LittleRedBook

MAPS

Google Maps, CityMapper,
Apple Maps, Paper maps

MAINSTREAM MEDIA

BBC, Channel 4, New York Times,
The Guardian, Podcasts

DEVICES / SMART APPS

Smartphone, Smartwatch,
Tablet, Laptop

GROUP / ASSOCIATIONS

Sports/Culture Communities,
Local/Global NGOs, Student Services,
Public Organizations, Embassies

INFRASTRUCTURES

Transport (Bus, Tube, Bikes etc),
Wifi Hotspots, CCTV

SPACES

University Buildings, Student Halls, Library,
Home, Places of Worship, Cultural Spaces,
Leisure Centre, Green Spaces/Parks

PEOPLE

Family, Friends, Co-Workers, Tutors,
University Peers, Councillors/Doctors

LEARNING RESOURCES

Library, Books, Journals, Google,
Keats, Wikipedia, ChatGPT,

ACTIVITIES

Sports, Culture, Study, Leisure,
Dating, Socialising

**DATA
EXPLOITATION**

GOSSIP / RUMOUR

**DIGITAL
SURVEILLANCE**

PROFILING

DIGITAL DETOX

**DIGITAL
OVERLOAD**

ADDICTION

FILTER BUBBLE

ECHO CHAMBER

DATA MINING

**ISOLATION /
LONELINESS**

MAGNET

MASK

**FOMO
(FEAR OF MISSING OUT)**

SECURITY / SAFETY

STEREOTYPING